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Institutional Support And Communication As Correlates Of Lecturers' Job Satisfaction In Colleges Of Education In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Institutional support is believed to be an important factor in attaining school organizational goals and ensuring lecturers' job satisfaction. With the combination of institutional support, lecturers are more likely to experience job satisfaction leading to higher productivity and better outcomes for both educators and students. Thus, the study specifically investigated institutional support as correlate of lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 697 lecturers from the two colleges of education in Anambra State. Sample size of 488 lecturers were drawn for the study through proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Structured rating scale: Institutional Support Rating Scale (ISRS) was used for data collection. The instrument was face and construct validated. Internal consistency co-efficient of 0.89, 0.85 and 0.87 were obtained for ISRS respectively, using Cronbach Alpha statistical method. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, t-test of correlation and multiple linear regressions statistics. The p-value was used to determine the significant difference at 0.05 level of significance for all hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that there is positive correlation between institutional support (staff development support, physical facilities support and instructional materials support) and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The findings also revealed that institutional support positively correlates to lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. However, the study established that there is positive correlation among the variables of the study, (R-value = 0.880). Thus, the study concluded that institutional support is an important variable that increases lecturers' job satisfaction. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that Ministry of Education should invest on improving staff development, physical facilities such as classrooms, offices, and recreational areas within colleges of education in Anambra State.

Keywords: Institutional Support, Communication, Lecturers' Job Satisfaction, Colleges, Education.

INTRODUCTION

Education could be seen as a tool for achieving socioeconomic and technological growth and development of any nation. It is an instrument par-excellence and the means of developing human intellect, technical skills, character and effective citizenship for self-reliance and effective national development (FRN, 2013). A simple way of appreciating education is that it is a tool and a necessary

weapon that is needed by every human being in order to effectively navigate this complex world (Madudili, 2022). Education in essence is the most effective instrument for academic progress, social mobilization, political survival and effective national development of a country, it constitutes the single largest enterprise in Nigeria. The educational policy of any nation is to achieve Education for All (E.F.A.) (Joseph, 2022). The priority is to ensure equitable access and improvement in the quality and efficiency of all level of education. A comprehensive view into the Nigerian educational system shows that, it is systematically structured into pre-primary, basic, secondary and tertiary education.

Tertiary education refers to all formal post-secondary education, including public and private universities, colleges of education, technical training institutes, and vocational schools. It is considered to be a major contributing factor to industrialization; political stability; national integration and unity; economic; and social stability of nations (Nebo et al., 2015). Tertiary education is instrumental in fostering growth, reducing poverty, and boosting shared prosperity. This means that tertiary education is the best means for developing national consciousness and very important in the development of high-level manpower for driving the techno-economic advancement of any serious nation. A highly skilled workforce, with lifelong access to a solid post-secondary education, is a prerequisite for innovation and growth: well-educated people are more employable and productive, earn higher wages, and cope with economic shocks better (Fabunmi, 2015). Tertiary education in Nigeria aims to provide advanced academic and professional training to students across a wide range of disciplines. The Nigerian tertiary education system is structured into various levels, including universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education.

Colleges of Education are institutions that specialize in providing teacher education and training programmes. They focus on preparing individuals to become educators, teaching them the necessary skills, knowledge, and pedagogical techniques required to effectively teach students at various levels, from early childhood to secondary education (Offorma & Chukwuma-Nosike, 2016). These colleges offer programs such as bachelor's degrees in education, postgraduate diplomas in education, and even advanced degrees in educational leadership or curriculum development. The primary aims of the Colleges of Education in Nigeria according to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) are to: prepare teachers for the country's basic education system through equipping them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to effectively teach various subjects at the primary and junior secondary levels; promote professionalism among teachers by providing them with a solid foundation in pedagogical principles, teaching methodologies, and classroom management techniques; and engage in research and innovation in the field of education, which includes conducting studies to improve teaching methods, curriculum development, and educational policies. In essence, colleges of education in Nigeria aimed to collectively contribute to the development of a well-trained and professional teaching workforce that can positively impact the education system and society as a whole in Nigeria. Admittedly, attainment of the primary objectives of colleges of education as specified in the policy document demands that teachers have crucial role to play in the school system.

Lecturers are the human resources that direct, instruct and impart skills, knowledge, values and morals to learners in higher institutions of learning. There is no doubt that the role of lecturers in curriculum implementation is enormous. Teachers are the engine that drives education of any nation. Ofoegbu (2017) opined that lecturers' interactions, views, duties and behaviour play vital roles in ensuring the achievement of educational objectives. These vital roles lecturers play make their job performance essential; hence, good performance of students depends upon effective instructional delivery by their lecturers. As professionals, lecturers need to be appropriate role models and exhibit to their students a commitment of their scholarly values and to life long-learning (Abdul et al., 2018). Lecturers are the machine that propels knowledge, information, ideas and skills transferred to learners. Agbonye (2016) observed that lecturers are the people that coordinate all the factors in teaching and learning process to promote the attainment of educational objectives. However, the success of any educational institution depends to a great extent on the job performance of the lecturers. Oleforo et al. (2015) opined that lecturers are those that make strident effort to improve human capital in the school. Lecturers are arguably the most important group of professionals for our nation's future; without lecturers, the education system will be crippled (Dutta & Sahney, 2016). This is to say that lecturers are the professionals that assist in academic, social and emotional development of students. From the definitions above, it is evident that lecturers are human capital developers whose jobs are illogical

without students in one hand and free expression of information on the other hand. However, to accomplish this primary task of achieving educational objectives depends to a great extent on lecturers' job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction refers to how content and happy an individual is with his or her job. Chamundeswari (2013) saw lecturers' job satisfaction as the degree to which lecturers perceive their total work situation to be an important part of their life and to be central to them and their identity because of the opportunity it affords them to satisfy their important needs. It is the extent to which the lecturers actively participate in the school activities and consider their performances important to their self-worth (Darshana, 2019). For lecturers, there are many factors that inform job satisfaction; they are intrinsic motivators and extrinsic motivators. The intrinsic motivators include a sense of achievement, the responsibility of working with the students, the lecturers' sense of control over the classroom, and the satisfaction of the work of teaching itself. Extrinsic motivators include the perceived support from administrators, school safety, benefits and compensation, and the availability of resources (Enwezor, 2021). In order to increase lecturers' job satisfaction for optimal educational result, Osondu (2022) suggested that the school management should solicit for institutional support from both government and private enterprises.

Institutional support consists of a set of physical facilities, software or processes, made available by the organization, which make learning success possible. In the concepts of institutional support, the words "Institution" and "Support" are particularly important. An institution is a structured and established organization, typically with a specific purpose, rules, and functions that guide its activities (Falola, 2016). Support on the other hand refers to providing assistance, aid, or help to someone or something in order to achieve a particular goal or address a need (Funmilayo et al., 2021). It can take various forms, such as emotional support, financial assistance, technical guidance, or physical aid, depending on the context and the nature of the situation. It is in line with this that institutional support was defined by Akudo (2022) as the resources, structures, and assistance provided by organizations, governments, or entities to individuals or groups to help them achieve their goals or address challenges. Similarly, Usman (2016) described it as the succor, funds, and structures provided by organizations, governments, or institutions to individuals, groups, or initiatives. Institutional support was also defined by Talabi (2012) as the resources, policies, and structures that organizations provide to help individuals or groups achieve their goals. From the foregoing, it can be deduced that institutional support encompasses various aspects like financial aid, training, mentorship, facilities, and guidance to ensure success or well-being within a particular institution or community. The concept defines all supports ranging from financial grants and facilities to guidance, networking opportunities, and access to expertise; that aimed at helping individuals or projects achieve their goals within a specific institutional framework. It is a holistic approach to management which affects every aspect of an organization with a view to building quality into it and ensuring teachers' job satisfaction (Falola et al., 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Colleges of education in Nigeria are expected to provide aspiring educators with the necessary knowledge, skills, and training to become effective teachers or educational professionals. These institutions are anticipated to focus on preparing individuals for careers in teaching by offering courses in pedagogy, curriculum development, classroom management, and educational psychology. Unfortunately, observation has revealed that in many cases, colleges of education students in Anambra state graduate as unprepared individuals with little or no competencies for teaching. Many times, they do not meet the satisfaction of employers, stakeholders and the society at large. This problem is believed to have contributed to the high rate of unemployment among graduates of colleges of education; since a reasonable percentage of them come out as unemployable graduates. Not only does this serve as an indicator that the colleges of education seem not to be attaining the objectives for which they are established, it is also an indication of possibility that lecturers' capacity to perform effectively is questionable. Again, there is a growing concern that relatively large numbers of lecturers in colleges of education in Anambra state are not satisfied in their job despite enormous investment by government at various levels.

Researcher's field of research shows that greater number of colleges of education across the country are in deplorable conditions, with dilapidated structures, inadequate and poorly maintained facilities,

non-motivated lecturers, poor communication, unfriendly school climate, poor school community relationship, disciplinary problems, poor curriculum development and instruction, guidance and counseling services, and evaluation of school programmes and activities. The poor state of the schools is not only unpleasant but also detrimental to the effective teaching and learning process as well as the quality of education the students receive. With the observations above, it appears that management of colleges of education in Nigeria cannot be fully adjudged to be efficient for improving lecturers' job satisfaction. This could also mean that essential elements of institutional support and communication for improved lecturers' job satisfaction may be inadequate and ineffective in colleges of education. The researcher is equally in doubt of the efficacy of institutional support and effectiveness of communication in colleges of education in Anambra State. Hence, the problem of this study is to examine institutional support and communication as correlates of lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine institutional support and communication as correlates of lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. In specific terms, the study sought to:

1. determine the correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State;
2. find out the correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State;
3. examine the correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State;

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?
2. What is the correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?
3. What is the correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?
2. There is no significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?
3. There is no significant correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?

Theoretical Framework

Theoretically, the study was anchored on Resource Dependence Theory. The theory was propounded by Jeffrey Pfeffer and Gerald Salancik in the year 1978. Resource dependence theory is a framework in organizational studies and sociology that seeks to explain how organizations are influenced and constrained by their external environment, particularly in terms of resource acquisition and utilization. It emerged as a response to the realization that organizations are highly dependent on external resources to survive and thrive. The central premise of the theory is that organizations depend on external resources and must secure critical resources from their external environment to survive and achieve their goals. These resources can include financial capital, human resources, information, technology, raw materials, and more. The theory emphasizes that resources are often scarce and unevenly distributed in the external environment. Consequently, organizations must engage in strategic actions and relationships to gain access to these resources. Resource dependence theory highlights the importance of inter-organizational relationships, such as alliances, partnerships, and collaborations, as a means for organizations to reduce their dependence on specific resource providers. By forming such relationships, organizations can diversify their resource base. The

proponents hold that one of the key tools used in resource dependence theory is the resource dependency matrix. It categorizes resources based on their importance and availability, helping organizations prioritize resource acquisition efforts.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study adopted the correlational research design. Correlational research design investigates the relationship between two or more variables to determine if a statistical association exists, without manipulating any of the variables. Ifeakor (2018) established that correlational research design aims at indicating the direction and magnitude of the relationship between or among the variables of the study. The study was conducted in Anambra State, South-East, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 697 lecturers from the two colleges of education in Anambra State - Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe and Federal College of Education Technical, Umunze (National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE], 2023). The lecturers were chosen for the study because they are the interpreters and implementers of schools' curriculum and policies that are mostly affected by institutional support in the school in relation to their job satisfaction; thus, they are better placed to provide useful data on the variables identified in the study. The sample size of the study was 488 lecturers (70% of the entire population) drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The instrument was used for data collection namely: Institutional Support Rating Scale (ISRS). The instrument (ISRS) was structured by the researcher from the review of related literature, consultation with experts and the specific purposes of the study. The first instrument – Institutional Support Rating Scale contains two sections, A and B. Section A sought background data of the respondents (lecturers) on name of the school. Section B contains 40 items spread across four clusters (A-C) to elicit data on institutional support. Cluster A contains 10 items on staff professional development support; cluster B contains 10 items on physical facilities support and cluster C contains 10 items on instructional materials support. Those items are placed on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The range of the scale weighted as 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Face and construct validation of the instruments (ISRS) were carried out. Face validation was done by three lecturers; two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to determine the reliability of the instruments. The coefficient values obtained for ISRS were 0.89, 0.85 and 0.87. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to answer the research questions. The (r) was used to determine the nature of the correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable of the study.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: *What is the correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Pearson r on the Correlation between Staff Professional Development Support and Lecturers' Job Satisfaction in Colleges of Education in Anambra State

Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
Staff Professional Development Support Lecturers' Job Satisfaction	472	0.806	Very High Positive Correlation

Results in Table 1 show that there is a very high positive correlation existing between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. This is evident by the value of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r, which is 0.806.

Research Question Two: *What is the correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Pearson r on the Correlation between Physical Facilities Support and Lecturers' Job Satisfaction in Colleges of Education in Anambra State

Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
Physical Facilities Support Lecturers Job Satisfaction	472	0.776	High Positive Correlation

Table 2 shows that the Pearson's $r=0.776$, indicating that there is a high positive relationship between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

Research Question Three: *What is the correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State?*

Table 3: Pearson r on the Correlation between Instructional Materials Support and Lecturers' Job Satisfaction in Colleges of Education in Anambra State

Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
Instructional Materials Support Lecturers Job Satisfaction	472	0.856	Very High Positive Correlation

Table 3 shows that there is a very high positive relationship existing between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. This is shown by the value of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r , which is 0.856.

Test of Hypotheses

The study tested the following hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance;

Hypothesis One

H_0 : There is no significant correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

H_1 : There is significant correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of Significance of T-Test of Correlation between Staff Professional Development Support and Lecturers' Job Satisfaction in Colleges of Education in Anambra State

Source of Variation N	R	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Staff Professional Development Support Lecturers' Job Satisfaction	472	0.806	21.67	1.96 Sig

Analysis in Table 4 shows that there is a significant correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.806) had r -cal value of 21.67 and p -value (0.001) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. However, the 1st null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant correlation between staff professional development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State was not upheld.

Hypothesis Two

H_0 : There is no significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

H_1 : There is significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of Significance of T-Test of Correlation between Teachers’ Perceived Organizational Justice scores and their Job Performance Scores

Source of Variation N		R	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Physical Facilities Support Lecturers Job Satisfaction	472	0.776	21.68	1.96	Sig

Analysis in Table 5 shows that there is a significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.776) had r-cal value of 21.68 and p-value (0.000) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. The 2nd null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State was therefore not upheld.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: There is no significant correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

H₁: There is significant correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of Significance of T-Test of Correlation between Male Teachers’ Self-leadership scores and their Job Performance Scores

Source of Variation N		R	t-cal	t-crit	Remark
Instructional Materials Support Lecturers Job Satisfaction	472	0.856	21.68	1.96	Sig

Table 6 shows that there is a significant correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.765) had r-cal value of 21.68 and p-value (0.000) which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the 3rd null hypothesis which asserted that there is no significant correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State was therefore not upheld.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results presented in Table 1 show that there is a very high positive correlation staff development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The results in Table 4 also show that there is significant correlation staff development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The implication is that lecturers in colleges of education agreed that there is positive and significant correlation between staff development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in the state. The rationale behind this is that the respondents acknowledged that access to ongoing staff training; provision of financial support for lecturers for attending external conferences; making online courses available for flexible professional development; access to resources such as research centers; and provision of opportunities for lecturers to attend international education conferences are factor that increase lecturers satisfaction. Supporting lecturers financially when pursuing advanced degrees or certifications; granting lecturers’ autonomy to request specific training based on their career goals; encouraging them to engage in interdisciplinary collaboration; engaging the lecturers in workshops on pedagogical techniques that enhance teaching skills; and recognizing them for their professional development achievements are determinants of lecturers’ job satisfaction. Specifically, the acceptance by the respondents that there is correlation between staff development support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra suggests that they accepted that staff development supports is crucial for maintaining lecturers’ morale and productivity as it forms the foundation for their teaching abilities.

The findings above are in line with the findings of Onyali and Alaeke (2021) who conducted a study on the relationship between teachers’ perception of staff personnel administrative practices of principals and their job performance in secondary schools in Enugu State. The findings indicated that

there was significant relationship between staff professional development practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Enugu State. The findings also agreed with the finding of Ukwuoma (2023) study that investigated the relationship between staff development programmes and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. The findings revealed that there is positive relationship between staff development programmes (conference, workshop, mentoring, & job rotation) and teachers' task performance. The finding of the study which established that staff professional development has very high correlation with lecturers' job satisfaction might be possibly due the fact that it enables them update their skills and broaden their knowledge for effective execution of tasks in the workplace. The technological advance, change and innovation in education institutions necessitated the staff professional development to enable teachers align with changes and use innovative devices to improve their job satisfaction and performance. Staff development prepares teachers for more responsibilities and higher productivity in the schools.

The correlations results shown in Table 2 revealed that there is high positive correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. In Table 5, the results also revealed that there is significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. This implies that lecturers in colleges of education in Anambra State accepted that there is positive and significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in the state. That is to say that safety measures like fire alarms are installed to protect the campus community; adequate classroom spaces are provided to facilitate interactive learning experiences; well-equipped laboratories are provided to support practical training in various academic disciplines; libraries are stocked with a wide range of books, journals, digital resources to support research and self-study; and computer labs with up-to-date technology are provided for students to access online resources. Lecturers also recognized that sports facilities are provided to encourage physical fitness; adequate accommodation facilities are made available within the school premises; lecture halls are equipped with audiovisual facilities for large-scale presentations; health clinic is provided to offer medical services to school personnel; and adequate restrooms are provided for the convenience of all. The acknowledgement of the relevance of physical facilities support lecturers' job satisfaction indicates that the respondents realize the importance of giving adequate attention to provision of school physical facilities for enhanced teachers' satisfaction, productivity and overall performance.

In agreement with the results of this study, the above results agree with one of the findings of Amie-Ogan and Tamunomiebi (2020) study which revealed that school physical facilities such as recreational facilities, welfare facilities, and health facilities etcetera were identified as instrumental for teachers' effectiveness and productivity in the teaching and learning process in Rivers State. The findings also concurred with the findings of a study in Turkey by Altunova and Kalman (2020). These researchers found that adequate provision of physical infrastructure, large class size, health facilities, and recreational facilities had positive relationship with teachers' job performance level. This implies that education providers should ensure that physical facilities are adequately provided for teachers to improve in their productivity.

Nonetheless, the overall results is not in concordance with the study by Ada (2013) which found that school physical facilities do not have significant effect on teachers' job performance. The study observed the school physical environment to be a performance influencing factor. Thus, it has to be noted that though dissimilar results were obtained by aforementioned studies, the difference in the findings may be attributed to chance. Clearly, some other reasons can be adduced for this. It could be as a result of the nature of the organizational climate prevalent in the schools studied by Ada. Indeed, it is a common knowledge that the types of climate existing in some schools do not encourage teachers to perform optimally hence, they lack job satisfaction even when physical facilities are adequately provided. Most schools do not encourage the teachers through various motivation strategies such as staff development, incentives increment in wages and salaries, staff promotion and so on. Equally, it could be that the study by Ada (2013) was carried out in schools experiencing unfriendly climate.

The results in Table 3 showed that there is very high positive correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. In Table 6, the results also revealed that there is significant correlation between instructional materials support

and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The explanation of the results is that lecturers in colleges of education in Anambra State agreed that there is positive and significant correlation between physical facilities support and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in the state. This implies that providing lecturers with subsidies for the purchase of required instructional materials; training lecturers in instructional material development which enhances their skills; providing lecturers with up-to-date textbooks often for instructional delivery; providing lecturers with subsidy for regular maintenance of instructional materials to ensure their longevity; and provision of Open Educational Resources (OER) for lecturers to reduce the cost of textbooks are important variables that improve lecturers job satisfaction. In specific terms, the acceptance by the respondents that instructional materials support correlates to lecturers job satisfaction suggests that as lecturers enjoy autonomy in the selection of instructional materials based on curriculum requirements; regularly evaluate instructional materials in their care to assess their effectiveness for proper replacement; and are encouraged to provide feedback on the relevance of instructional materials to ensure their relevance their overall job satisfaction tends to increase. This implies making available an inclusive instructional materials for lecturers to accommodate diverse teaching styles and providing them with visual aids to illustrate various concepts visually are associated with better job contentment and outcomes in terms of fulfilling the responsibilities and goals of the teaching profession.

The findings on correlation between instructional materials support and lecturers' job satisfaction tally with that of Safiullah et al. (2022) whose study discovered that the use of social media and new media promotes political marketing. Safiullah et al.'s study revealed that poor information dissemination during political activities and apathy during elections are the functions of ineffective use of social media and new media during political marketing. The findings are in tandem with the earlier findings of Kaku and Arthur (2020) who found that instructional materials are useful in teaching and learning of Economics. They ascertained that instructional materials help teachers to involve learners in classroom presentation and also in explaining concept to students; which in turn increase their job satisfaction. The findings also corroborate the findings of Adelabu (2012) which found that instructional materials significantly affect students' achievement and teachers' efficiency in instructional delivery. They maintained that students taught with instructional materials achieve higher in their studies than those taught without instructional materials. They emphasized the role of instructional materials among which is ensuring effective instructional delivery, retention and making learning more permanent is a catalyst to increased teachers' job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, it was found that there is positive and significant correlation between institutional support (staff development support, physical facilities support and instructional materials support) and lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. The findings also revealed that intuitional support positively and significantly correlates to lecturers' job satisfaction in colleges of education in Anambra State. Finally, the study established that there is positive and significant joint correlation among the variables of the study. However, the study concluded that institutional support is important factors that increase lecturers' job satisfaction.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings in the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators should introduce regular professional development programmes tailored to the needs and interests of lecturers in Anambra State colleges of education.
2. School management should create a supportive work environment that values lecturers' contributions, encourages collaboration, and provides adequate resources for teaching and research.
3. Ministry of Education should invest in improving physical facilities such as classrooms, offices, and recreational areas within colleges of education in Anambra State. Upgrading infrastructure can positively impact staff morale and job satisfaction, leading to a more conducive environment for lecturers.
4. Government and school management should conduct a comprehensive analysis of the current instructional materials available in colleges of education in Anambra State to identify any

gaps or deficiencies and lecturers' perspectives on the adequacy and effectiveness of the available ones.

5. School administrators should establish regular feedback channels where lecturers can anonymously provide input on administrative support services.

REFERENCES

- Abdul, G. K. A., Ying-Leh L., & Shamihah, B. S. (2018). Principal transformational leadership and teachers' motivation. *Asian Education Studies*, 3(1), 36-42.
- Ada, T. O. (2013). Analysis and the availability of physical facilities and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 5(1), 14-21.
- Adelabu, M. A. J. (2012). Improving learning infrastructure and environment for sustainable quality assurance practices in secondary schools. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 1(1), 61-66.
- Agbonye, C. O. (2016). *Physical facilities in secondary schools in Owerri Education Zone of Imo State* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Imo State University, Owerri.
- Akudo, F. U. (2022). Management support and locus of control as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Anambra State. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 4(1), 41-51.
- Altunova, N., & Kalman, M. (2020). Factors affecting classroom teachers' job performance: A qualitative-dominant analysis with Q-Sorting. *Research in Pedagogy*, 10(2), 285-312.
- Amie-Ogan, O. T., & Tamunomiebi, B. (2020). Influence of school plant planning on teachers' effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Okrika and Ogu-Bolo Local Government Areas of Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 8(4), 98-107.
- Chamundeswari, S. (2013). Job satisfaction and performance of school teachers. *International Journal of Academic Research and Social Sciences*, 3(5), 420-428.
- Darshana, S. (2019). Job satisfaction and professional commitment of teacher educators: An empirical study. *International Journal of Recent Science Resources*, 10(09), 34651-34657.
- Dutta, V. & Sahney, T. (2016). School leadership and its impact on student achievement: The mediating role of school climate and teacher job satisfaction. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(6), 941-958. Doi:10.1108/IJEM-12-2014-0170.
- Enwezor, C. H. (2021). Relationship between principals' human resource management practices and teachers' job satisfaction in secondary schools in Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 2(1), 137-150.
- Fabunmi, M. (2015). Historical analysis of educational policy formation in Nigeria: Implications for educational planning and policy. *International Journal of African and African American Studies*, 4(2), 32-45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/0951340510599635>.
- Falola, H. O., Oludayo, O. A., Igbinoba, E. E., Salau, O. P., & Borishade, T. T., (2018). Measuring work engagement strategies and employees' behavioural outcomes in Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Business Retail Management Resources*, 13(2), 98-108.
- Fashiku, C. O. (2016). Leaders' communication pattern: A predictor of lecturers' job performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*, 4(2), 103-126. doi: 10.17583/ijelm.2016.1848.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National policy on education, (6th edition)*.
- Funmilayo, F. A., Adebawale, J. A., Arinola, O. G., & Mutiat, Y. S. (2021). Institutional support and collection development practices in private university libraries in South-West Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 6(3), 222-234.
- Ifeakor, A. C. (2018). *What to write and how to write research proposal and report*. Lincel Publishers.
- Joseph, A. A. (2022). *Managerial strategies and school plant management as correlates of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State* [Unpublished doctoral thesis]. Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus Anambra State.

- Kaku, G. N., & Arthur, L. W. (2020). Instructional materials for teaching Economics: Availability and utilization in secondary schools in Nyandarua County, Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(3), 1-14.
- Madudili, C. G. (2022). Quality management principles and school resource management as correlates of teachers' job performance in Unity Schools in South-East, Nigeria.
- National Commission for Colleges of Education. (2022). *NCCE Reviews NCE Standards to Improve Teacher Quality*. The Eagle Online. Retrieved 2022-05-07.
- Nebo, C. S., Nwankwo, P. N., & Okonkwo, R. I. (2015). The role of effective communication on organizational performance: A study of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. *Zainab Arabian Research Society for Multidisciplinary Issues*, 4(8), 131-145.
- Offorma, G. C., & Chukwuma-Nosike, C. (2016). Sustainable development goals: Enriching teacher education curriculum for quality education and lifelong learning. *Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Education*, 13(1), 1-9.
- Ofoegbu, F. (2017). *Educational management new perspective: School personnel management*. Amfitop Books.
- Oleforo, N. A., Ikpe, U. I., & Bassey, E. A. (2015). Management strategies and secondary school teachers' job performance in Akwa-Ibom South Senatoria District. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education*, 4(2), 151-158.
- Onyali, L. C. & Alaeke, G. A. (2021). Relationship between teachers' perception of staff personnel administrative practices of principals and their job performance in secondary schools in Enugu State. *International Journal of Research*, 8(8), 63-79.
- Osondu, E. C. (2022). *Principals' motivational strategies as predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Idemili South Local Government Area of Anambra State* [Unpublished bachelor project]. Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Safiullah, M. D., Pathak, P., & Singh, S. (2022). The impact of social media and news on political marketing: An empirical study of 2014 Indian General Election. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 26(4), 536-550.
- Talabi, A. S. (2012). Employees' training and development for optimum productivity: The role of Industrial Training Fund (ITF), Nigeria. *Journal of International Institute for Science, Technology and Education*, 2(4), 50-58.
- Ukwuoma, S. C. (2023). Relationship between staff development programmes and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State [unpublished bachelor project]. Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.
- United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (2018). *Historical context of school buildings and facilities program*. [www.https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337511604_School_Plant_Organization](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337511604_School_Plant_Organization).
- Usman, Y. D. (2016). Educational resources an integral component for effective school administration in Nigeria. *Journal on Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(13), 27-37.